

Robust Watermarking in Digital Image Using Neural Network and Glowworm Optimization

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Abstract:

Digital watermarking has been recognized as a very vast research field to handle the challenges that occur during the distribution of digital content over a network or the internet. The digital content may be misused by an unauthorized person, or its copyright may be illegally claimed by someone who is not actually involved in the creation of this digital content. So, it is highly required to overcome these issues to protect the digital contents from unauthorized persons. Digital watermarking techniques are very useful in this regard. In this technique, a secret message is embedded imperceptibly into the actual digital content. The embedded secret information is called a "watermark". The watermark may be a logo of an organization or company, some hidden text, the author's secret serial number, or images of some special importance or a label. It could be further used for different applications, such as copyright protection, authentication, and temper detection. In the paper, the discrete wavelet transform (DWT) has been applied for image segmentation. Optimization of the segmented image is achieved through the Glowworm Swarm Optimization algorithm, and lastly, the Advanced Encryption System is used to encrypt the watermarked image. The method proposed in this paper will improve security, performance, and efficiency as compared with already existing techniques.

Keywords - Discrete Wavelet Transform, Advanced Encryption System, Glow-worm Swarm Optimization, PSNR, MSE.

1. INTRODUCTION

It is very important to consider the security of data in the modern era because a large amount of data is sent on digital media or distributed over the internet. The data may be in the form of images, text, audio, or video. Such data are distributed in digital form. Any intruder can copy such data very easily without damaging its quality. So, the need to protect data from an illegal person becomes important. The message is stored in digital form because it is very convenient to reproduce the information after decryption, retransmit data if required, and manipulate the data. This will facilitate removing a watermark and violating a copyright or casting the same watermark after altering the data to forge the proof of authenticity[1]. The design of techniques for maintaining the ownership of information is the basis for the development of future multimedia services. Additionally, the general idea of encrypting the information in digital content has very large-scale applications that go beyond copyright protection and authentication. The methods involved in such applications are generally referred to as "information hiding. Metadata describes additional features of an image. Although this metadata may also be stored in the digital image file header, this approach may have many limitations. Usually, when a file is converted to another format (e.g., from TIFF to JPEG or to BMP), the metadata is lost. Also, cropping or any other form of image manipulation damages the metadata. Finally, the metadata may be attached to an image until the image is in digital form, but it is lost immediately when the image is printed. Data encryption allows the metadata to travel without concern for image format or image state[2].

2. DIGITAL WATERMARKING

Similarity between Watermarking and Communication System

Watermarking is the process of superimposing of some logo or text at the top of a document and transporting this information over a channel consisting of the original work to be watermarked. This watermarked information is sent from sender to receiver by using communication channel or trough internet. In order to transmit the discrete information over a communication channel, a modulator transforms each symbol of the encoded information into a suitable form which is needed for transmission. Since physical media always have noise to some to some extent so information may be destroyed during transmission. The different forms of noise that can disturb the transmission are driven by the channel characteristics. On receiver end, the Demodulator processes the transmitted sequence and gives an output that have counterpart of the encoded sequence. The channel decoder transforms the output of demodulator into a binary sequence which gets estimated with the sequence being transmitted. The transmission can be further treated according to the security it provides against active attacks and passive attacks. Active attacks are always trying to disable communication and passive attacks may try to monitor the communication[2].

Fig 1.1 Basic Communication Systems[2]

Properties of Digital Watermarking

To understand process of watermarking and its applications, one needs to know the properties of digital watermarks in deep. Few fundamental characteristics are discussed below:

- **The Imperceptibility**

This is the most vital characteristics of all watermarking techniques. The watermark must be superimposed in such a manner that the resulted image is not distorted visually. This property maintains the robustness of the information. There is a need to get optimal balancing between imperceptibility and robustness[3].

- **Robustness**

Robustness is another important property of watermarking techniques. Most techniques require that the watermark should be recovered even if image is being attacked by intruders and this attack may be passive or active[4].

- **Payload**

Total number of bits of watermarked image is called payload. The amount of information bits to be superimposed always depends upon the application. It is normally considered that the more the watermark bits (payload) in an image the higher is the robustness of watermark[3].

- **Security**

Encryption techniques like AES or DES are used to secure watermark during transmission. This can be achieved by using the keys. The use of Keys makes the information more secure (as in case of cryptography)[3].

TYPES OF DIGITAL WATERMARKS

The watermark which is embedded into the digital content can be of various types as shown in Figure 1.2

Fig 1.2 Types of Watermarks

- **Visible and Invisible Watermark**

This type of watermark after embedding to host image is visible to the user that means this type of watermarks are visible to the outside world after watermarking. The watermark normally recognizes the owner of information and consists of a logo or seal of the company. Whereas in case of invisible watermark, after embedding the watermark is invisible to user without degrading the image quality. Invisible Watermarks are generally be a signature and company's logo. Currently most researches focus on invisible watermark rather than visible watermark[5].

- **Image Adaptive Watermark**

Such kinds of watermarks are generally transform-based. They are locally adapting watermark strength to the content of the image[1].

- **Fragile and Robust Watermark**

In case of fragile watermark if there are any small changes to image, the watermark distorted or broken easily. It is used to check the integrity of the image that means its intention is not to check robustness but to check the occurrence of attacks on image. On the other hand, these types of watermarks are difficult to remove from watermarked image[5].

- **Non-Blind and Blind Watermarking**

The original image must be needed when detecting the watermark. As we know that no original image is required blind watermarking during detecting process; hence blind watermarking is less robust as compared to non-blind watermarking[5].

- **Private Watermarking**

Private watermarking technique is also called non-blind watermarking. Only one key is used which is not known to any one for encryption and decryption. Also, Original image is required for watermark detection purpose[6].

- **Asymmetric and Symmetric Watermarking**

In this type of watermarking technique, the keys used superimposing and fetching the watermark are strictly different. It should have the property that any user without being able to remove but can read the watermark [9].

- **Steganographic and Non-Steganographic Watermark**

In this watermarking technique the users are not aware of the presence of watermark in the image and in non-steganographic technique the content users are totally aware of the existence of watermark in the image. These watermarks protect the images after these are resampled. Steganographic watermarking is used in fingerprint whereas non-steganographic techniques can be used to prevent piracy[9].

Advanced Encryption Standard (AES) Algorithm for Digital Watermarking

Firstly, an image is selected for transmission. This input image is then partitioned into wavelet sub-bands. Since there are HL, LH, HH and LL sub-bands, we choose only LL sub-band for encryption purpose because majority of the energy is concentrated in LL sub-band having relatively lower frequency. The LL sub-band is encrypted by AES-128 encryption algorithm. Only a part of the image is selected to for encryption instead of the entire image. This will reduce the computational time. There are 10 rounds in AES-128. This minimizes the number of if-else-then loops. Here input plaintext matrix is transformed into state matrix by AES. State matrix is generated by computing hexadecimal value of input matrix. This state matrix is given as input variable to the forthcoming processes of encryption. State matrix is obtained by performing rearrangements the matrix of plain text.

It iteratively loops through the steps as Add round key, Sub bytes, Shift rows, and Mix columns. The Add round key block get operated in bitwise XOR function of the state matrix and round key matrix. The Sub bytes block is applied to the S-box to input matrix. This block performs the substitution function where each byte of input matrix is swapped by the value in S-box.

Glowworm Swarm Optimization for Digital Watermarking

Glow-worm swarm optimization exploits the collective nature of glow-worms. Glow-worms are a lightening bug whose brightness depends on a substance known as luciferin. The value of luciferin decides with which intensity a glow-worm will glow. Higher the value of luciferin, brighter the bug and lesser value lead to less light intensity with which the glowworm glows. Each glow-worm has its own sensor range and decision range. Sensor range determines the neighbor of glowworm and decision range determines which glow-worms can move towards it. There are two phases: movement phase and luciferin updating phase. The movement of glow-worm in the search space is such that they move towards the glow-worm that glows brighter than it and that resides in its circular sensor range. After that the decision range of each neighbor is checked to see whether the glow-worm that wants to move towards them resides in it or not. If multiple such neighbors exist, in whose decision range the glow-worm in question resides then probability is being calculated to find the neighbor for final movement. Luciferin updating phase updates the luciferin value of each glow-worm according to its current luciferin value and according to the goodness of the new position attained. The decision range of each glow-worm is also updated which is governed by current decision range and the number of neighbors found. Hence moving towards glowworm that has better luciferin value leads to an ultimate arrangement, that is optimized. In the paper the work has been proposed a novel feature selection algorithm for image steganalysis-Glow Worm Swarm Optimization. To the best of the insight, this is the first endeavor to utilize Glow-worm Swarm optimization with Extreme Learning machine (ELM) for choosing the diminished list of feature set for image steganalysis[7].

Feature Selection using Glowworm Swarm Optimization Algorithm

Glow-worm swarm optimization algorithm exploits the swarm intelligence nature of an insect known as “glow-worm” (fireflies). As the name says glow-worm are the lighting bug that are capable of emitting light at different intensities. The intensity of light with which a glow-worm glows depends on the amount of luciferin (a substance) emitted by the glowworm. Lesser the amount of luciferin lesser is the intensity of light with which glow-worm glows and vice-versa. Glowworm flies in their search space and move closer to glowworm that glows brighter than them. Each glow-worm has a circular sensor range (R_s) that describes its neighborhood. We have used Euclidian Distance to measure the distance between two glow-worms. When a glow-worm is found to be moved in the search space; those glowworms are considered that tend to fall in its sensor range. Glow-worm that are found moving outside the sensor range are definitely not being considered. The glow-worms that have higher luciferin in the sensor range are shortlisted as few of the final glow-worms for movement. Here every glow-worm may be considered one by one and respective decision range is being checked and verified to check the glow-worm that is hungry to come near to them resides in their decision range (R_d) or not. The direct probability of movement towards a neighbor (j) is given by equation 4.1

$$p_j(t) = \frac{l_j(t) - l_i(t)}{\sum_{k \in N_i(t)} l_k(t) - l_i(t)}$$

Equation – 4.1[7]

Here, $j \in N_i(t)$; $N_i(t) = \{j \text{ such that } d_{i,j}(t) < r_i(t); l_i(t) < l_j(t)\}$, where t is the time index, $d_{i,j}(t)$ represents the Euclidian Distance between glow-worms i and j at time t and l_i corresponds to the luciferin value of the i th glow-worm

. The neighbor which has the highest probability is the best candidate for the movement and the glow-worm moves towards it. The luciferin value and hence the intensity with which a glow-worm glows is also updated. In this proposed feature selection algorithm using glowworm swarm optimization, each glow-worm is considered to be an agent whose position is represented as bit string. Bit string of 1 and 0 represents the presence and absence of features. ‘1’ signifies that the corresponding features present and ‘0’ means the corresponding

feature is absent.

Steps for the Algorithm

The main steps of the proposed algorithm are:

- **Initialization**

The agents (glow-worm) are initialized in this phase i.e., each agent's position is randomly assigned with bit string that has random number of features on. Other parameters used are:

- Circular Sensor Range, of some percentage of number of features, N.
- Randomly initialized decision range, rd which varies between 0 to rs.
- Luciferin decay constant, ρ and enhancement constant, γ whose value varies between 0 to 1 are also set in this phase.

- **Luciferin Update Phase:**

In this phase, the luciferin value is updated for each glow-worm. The luciferin is updated by the formula:

$$l_j(t+1) = (1 - \rho) l_j(t) + \gamma J_j(t+1) \quad (4.2)$$

This equation is governed by two parameters "Luciferin Enhancement Constant" (γ) and "Luciferin Decay Constant" (ρ)

. The decay constant specifies by what fraction the new luciferin value should be dependent on the old value and the enhancement constant specifies by what percentage the new luciferin value should depend on the classifier accuracy is obtained after the glow-worm reaches its new position. The value of both decay and enhancement lies between 0 and 1. Here $J(t)$ corresponds to the value of the objective function at agent location of j at time t and l_i corresponds to the luciferin value of the i th glow-worm[8].

- **Movement Phase:**

This phase includes several steps and all steps are followed for each glow-worm.

- All the neighbors of the glow-worm are determined that have luciferin value greater than their own luciferin value. The neighbors are found using Euclidian Distance.
- For each neighbor the decision range is to be checked to observe if the glow-worm that wants to move towards them lie in the decision range or not.
 - If multiple such neighbors exist then probability is calculated for each neighbor as specified in equation (eq 4.1.1) above and the glow-worm moves towards the glow-worm with highest probability.
 - Since we are dealing with bit strings hence the movement of a glow-worm towards other glow-worm is in form of bit flips. The number of bits to be flipped is calculated by multiplying the step size s (a random variable between 0 and 1) with the Euclidian distance between the two glow-worms. Then bit-wise matching of feature bit string of both glow-worms is done. If corresponding bits are not same, the bit in the string corresponding to the glow-worm that is moving is flipped to match it to the bit of the string corresponding to glow-worm towards which it is moving. This is done until required number of bits is flipped. This marks the end of glowworm movement and the glow-worm reaches its new position[7].

1. After that the decision range rd for every glow-worm is updated as per to equation:

$$rd(t+1) = \min\{rs, \max\{0, rd(t) + \beta(nt - |N_i(t)|)\}\} \quad (4.3)$$

The (nt) is a parameter or variable that controls the number of neighbors a glow-worm has in each iteration and β is a constant.

2. Both the luciferin updating and the movement phase are repeated a predefined number of times.
3. Now to get the solution, the best glow-worm (the bit string with the maximum classifier's

accuracy) is chosen among all the glow-worms.

Fig 1.3 Glow-worm Algorithms.

The Glowworm Optimization is shown in the fig given below-

Fig 1.4 Optimized Results Upper

2.4.5 Neural Network

Neural Network is one of the most important steps for training and it has fast reaction time and response time which will train the system in efficient manner. The other advantages are:

- Moderately easy to practice
- Can estimated any function, irrespective to its linearity
- Countless for complex difficulties like pattern recognition[9].

Fig 1.5 Neural Networks

3. RESULTS

Various mechanism and techniques have been discovered to protect the ownership rights various digital contents by using watermarking techniques on gray and color digital images. This integrates the concept of watermarking and image processing.

A watermarking technique facilitates us to identify image that looks in various shades of brightness used for the security in digital image processing. It is generally the basic approach of hiding digital information in an image. It may be recycled or retrieved to confirm or justify the genuineness or truthfulness of the data.

Here the hybridization approach is implemented which is using DWT for the hybridization with Neural and AES for the security in the testing phase.

Fig 1.6 Mean Square Error Rate

Fig 1.7 Peak Signal to Noise Ratio

The figure 1.7 shows the PSNR. A highly efficient watermarking system should have high PSNR.

Fig 1.8 Watermark Image

The above figure shows the image which is to be water marked and embedded in the original image and which must be extracted at the end after the embedding process. The MSE Rate (Mean Square Error Rate) must be low and PSNR must be high for the highly efficient system.

Table 1: Performance Comparison

Parameters	MSE	PSNR (dB)
Sample 0	0.0000120	56.9
Sample 1	0.0000217	48.1692
Sample II	0.0000318	56.45
Sample III	0.0000248	49.43
Sample IV	0.0000125	51.23

Fig 1.9 MSE Comparison

Here figure 1.9 depicts the Mean Square Error rate comparison on different samples and it shows that the proposed system is well suited to get lesser error rate.

Fig 1.10 PSNR

Comparison Here figure 1.10 depicts peak signal to noise ratio.

Parameter	Base	Proposed
Error_Rate	0.50	0.000012

Table 2: Error Rate

Fig.1.11 Error Rate

Here figure 1.11 depicts the comparison between the base and proposed approach where proposed approach is well suited to maintain low error rates as compared to the others base solutions.

4. CONCLUSION AND FUTURE SCOPE

Modern digital watermarking can protect the copyrights of an image from various illegal and unauthorized ownerships. It also deals with the security of an image on the communication network. The digital watermarking technique proposed in this research work is comparatively much better than special-domain watermarking. The watermarking technique here is very suitable for getting rid of attacks like noise and sharpening. In the present proposed work, the overall system is dealt with using the discrete wavelet transform (DWT) for decomposition purposes. The segmentation is done by applying low pass and high pass filters. Optimization is achieved by applying glow-worm swarm algorithms, and lastly, a neural network is used for training the system. The AES (Advanced Encryption Scheme) is used to protect the system from various spoofing attacks, which means the security measure is achieved by applying AES algorithms. Hence, it is clear from the evaluated results in the proposed system that a high ratio of signal to noise is achieved with lower error rates.

The discrete wavelet transform technique can be used here for watermarking an image data file. So, we can summarize that the digital watermarking technique is a very suitable approach to protecting the copyrights of digital properties. Various digital watermarking techniques are used for various types of needs. However, it is not always possible to satisfy all the requirements at the same time. So, PSNR (peak-signal-to-noise ratio) can be used to compare the noise ratios of different samples used for research work. There may be scope for future study in the present study. A future study can be implemented by analyzing watermarking on different machine learning algorithms and comparing the signal-to-noise ratio on different platforms. Secondly, we can attempt to do the research work by focusing on types of attacks and evaluating the performance of the entire system.

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